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ACTIVITY OF LIBRARIES OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIVE SPACE

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The aim of the article is to systematise, summarise new knowledge on the activities of libraries of vocational education institutions in the information and communication space, to consider specific activities in terms of present and prospects for their development.

The research methodology was based on the general scientific principles of unity of theory and practice, systematics, complexity, and comprehensiveness of knowledge. The use of general scientific (description, analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalisation) and special (bibliographic, sample observation, grouping, content analysis) methods at the empirical and theoretical levels of research contributed to achieving this goal.

The scientific novelty of the research is to generalise and systematise new and known knowledge concerning the activities of libraries of vocational education institutions in the information and communication space in terms of nowadays and prospects for its development within one research.

Conclusions. Current conditions of transformation of the learning process focused on distance education and the rapid development of digital technology pose new challenges to the libraries of vocational education institutions. The quarantine constraints that libraries faced in 2020-2021 demonstrated the need to reformat rapidly various types of library services into an online format. The most promising channel for promoting any information or resources today is the Internet.

The use of Internet technology in libraries is now mandatory for every librarian. Librarians should not only focus on information and communication resources and technologies, including the Internet but also apply this knowledge in practice.

Thus, the introduction of Internet tools in the activities of libraries of vocational education institutions is an urgent necessity. Librarians can effectively use a great variety of Internet services in their daily work and bring vocational education institutions' information and library services to a qualitatively new level.

Keywords: libraries, vocational education institutions, Internet, social networks, information and communicative space.

PROBLEM SETTING

The realisation of the potential of the information society now requires consensus solutions, introduction of innovative programmes and projects.

Among the priority national projects aimed at solving systemic social development problems in Ukraine, one of the main ones is the e-Ukraine project, which aims to promote the use of information society for the development of humankind, society, and states. The project's objectives are to create the necessary prerequisites for forming effective, efficient and comprehensive informational support in Ukraine. The set of elements of this process will serve as a reliable basis for building a new information society in our country. Some directions of practical implementation of the project coincide with the primary mission and the status of a modern library and information centres supporting access to information in electronic form. A variety of forms of information services, which are due to the rapid informational support of educational institutions and their integral part – libraries, in strategic terms, must ensure:

Preservation of national, cultural, historical and legal heritage on digital media, creation of electronic libraries;

Integration of digital resources into the world socio-cultural space;

Providing open access to research results (electronic archives, repositories);

Publication of research results of educational institutions (institutional repositories);

Creation of a Single Window of educational resources;

Providing access to digital content at any time, etc.

Taking into consideration those mentioned above, we note that the largest libraries in North America and the European continent have already concluded as follows: library holdings cannot be concealed, but, on the contrary, free access must be provided (free or conditionally paid) to their e-copies via the Internet. This approach, in our opinion, creates favourable conditions for expanding the worldview of young people, supporting the research of scientists, raising the prestige and popularity of the library itself, disseminating information concerning the country's cultural values, and raising the status of the country in the world. In this direction, it has been done a lot in Ukraine as well. Certain steps, in fact, accelerate the movement of society to the civilisation of information technology knowledge. In particular, the project ElibUkr «Electronic Library of Ukraine: creation centres of knowledge in universities» provides users access to e-information and resources through ElibUkrOA multi-university archives (almost 50 universities joined the project). Domestic State target national-cultural programme for creating Library-XXI unified information library system serves to introduce gradually into scientific circulation unique documents that have historical and cultural value not only for Ukraine but also for the world community.

In this context, an important task of each library of vocational (vocational) education institutions in this context is a new format of information support for pupils, changing the role and functions of the librarian in the information and educational environment. The librarian of a vocational education institution should keep up with the progress in pedagogical technologies and effectively use computer and telecommunication technologies and navigate cyberspace. There is professionalism that helps librarians play a role as an information mediator for both learners and teachers, determining the library's participation in the educational process, no less important than the teacher's participation.

Therefore, the primary strategies for implementing the development of libraries of vocational education institutions (hereinafter referred to as VEI) in the online space for librarians should be: creating information products of a new format, introducing new library utilities and services, anticipating all possible requests of information users, expanding new access to information and creating a qualitatively new communication with users. If you respond flexibly to the needs of your users – new projects and forms of work appear on their own. The main thing is to be ready for challenges and be inspired to implement unexpected ideas.

Thus, the introduction of Internet tools in the activities of libraries of VEI is a necessity. Librarians can effectively use a wide variety of Internet services in their daily work to bring the information and library services of libraries of VEI to a qualitatively new level.

At the same time, it is necessary to mention that the analysis of the activity of libraries of vocational education institutions in information and communicative space has not been conducted as the main attention had been paid to libraries of higher education institutions. This article is dedicated to this issue.

ANALYSIS OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE

Scholars in their works highlighted various aspects of the development of the library as a social institution. Thus, the problems of library science were studied by V. Ilganaeva, L. Filippova, J. Schreiber, Iu. Grikhanov, V. Horovyi, M. Slobodyanyk; changes in information requests of users – P. Kulish, T. Novalska, T. Koval, O. Mastipan, O. Lopata; introduction of the newest technology in library practice – D. Solovyanenko, L. Kostenko, Al Tavalbekh Serkhan Ahmed, O. Voskoboinikova-Huzieva, L. Kononuchenko and others.

An important trend in the functioning of the modern library system is the active use of electronic information technology. It is facilitated and encouraged by strengthening globalisation in all spheres of human life (technical and technological, political, economic, etc.) and increasing the social demand for information support in the development of the information society.

Researchers pay considerable attention to the transformation of the library sphere in the digital environment. In the professional literature, at domestic and international conferences, various aspects of the modernisation of the library system are considered. As L. Filippova (1998) emphasises in his dissertation, it is necessary to study carefully the problems that objectively arise in the context of information support of society: theoretical, organisational, and technological. Moreover, at the level of the third group, issues of an applied nature can be addressed by conditionally dividing them into «computer-technology», which reflects the peculiarities of the organisation of computer technology in bibliographic activities. The next «communication-technology» reflects the peculiarities of organising the use of telecommunication technology of the Internet in bibliographic activity, features of search, service and presentation of e-bibliographic information in world information resources.

An electronic library is an information system that allows you to store securely and effectively use a variety of collections of electronic documents (text, visual, audio, video, etc.), localised in the system, as well as accessible through telecommunications networks.

As Professor V. Horovyi (2006) rightly points out, the transition of libraries to new technologies, and organisational solutions due to growing public demand, is characterised by a mixed system of traditional and contemporary approaches to customer service, which gives reason to call these institutions hybrid.

To some extent, new virtual-digital forms of storing, presenting and receiving information in library institutions became a reflection of the law of metamorphism of the library, substantiated by Iu. Grykhanov (2001). The essence of the law is that the library transforms (modifies) the forms of acquisition, storage, and provision of documentary information in parallel with the development of its recording and transmission methods and means of communication. The metamorphism of the library in the electronic age is a determining factor for its structural reorganisation, primarily for restructuring the library system. As Ye. Voskoboinikova-Huzieva (2003) points out, library transformation, or so-called hybridisation, is a natural reaction of the social system to the influence of the external environment. As a result, a new type of library has emerged, where electronic and traditional printed information sources are presented in a comprehensive and integrated way and are provided to both direct and remote users.

The theory of library science has already recorded the fact that global informational support has advanced libraries among the most important, in terms of meeting the social needs of society, and the institutions of formation and dissemination of information resources. In the future, libraries should intensify the development of information functions, become universal information centres, and provide free and unrestricted access to information for all members of society. The role of libraries in production, research, and education, in the development of democracy and market relations, is growing.

Achievements in microelectronics and improvements in computer technology and software have made it possible in a historically short time to move from text processing to the introduction of multimedia, hypermedia and video technology. At the beginning of the 21st century, almost all national libraries dealt with resources on various media – paper, digital (electronic) and optical disks, video and audio cassettes, magnetic tapes, etc. Internet services and technologies significantly expand traditional forms of library services. New forms and directions are emerging and developing due to the modern technological base of means of communication – telecommunications and the Internet. Al Tawalbeh Serhan Ahmed (2002) dissertation is dedicated to this issue, which arises in the process of global information support for society. The researcher emphasises the specific features of computer and telecommunications technology and the need for their use in libraries. In particular, he notes that the communication environment of the Internet contains the most popular and promising services for the library sector:

WWW (World Wide Web), on its basis, it is possible to use the latest audio, video and multimedia technology (tools) for organising TV and video conferences, etc.;

An E-mail has become an important communication channel for remote subscribers' remote service; for library document exchange in the framework of such a new service as electronic delivery.

MAIN RESEARCH MATERIAL

In 2021, the Division of Scientific and Methodological Support of Vocational Education at the Institute of Education Content Modernization, State Scientific Institution, decided to analyse the digital services by libraries of vocational education institutions in Ukraine. To this end, the division has prepared a questionnaire to obtain objective information concerning this issue from the regions of Ukraine. Three oblasts of Ukraine were selected for this study: Dnipropetrovsk, Zaporizhzhia and Kharkiv. In each of these oblasts, three vocational education institutions were selected. There was Pershotravensk Mining Lyceum, Dnipro Higher Vocational School of Construction, Kryvyi Rih Centre for

Vocational Education Metallurgy and Mechanical Engineering State Educational Institution in the Dnipropetrovsk oblast. In the Zaporizhzhia oblast, there was Berdiansk Centre for Vocational Education State Educational Institution, Multidisciplinary Centre for Vocational Education State Educational Institution, Vasylivskiy Vocational Lyceum State Educational Institution. In Kharkiv oblast, there was Lyubotyn Vocational Lyceum of Railway Transport, Kharkiv Regional Center for Vocational Education of Printing Media Technology and Mechanical Engineering State Educational Institutio, Kupiansk Regional Centre for Vocational Education State Educational Institution. In the mentioned institutions, 20 teachers and 40 pupils answered the questionnaire.

In addition, scientific and methodological centres of vocational education in these areas were involved in this research.

The survey involved pupils and teachers of the following programme subject areas: Agriculture, Cooking, Beverage, Trade, Hotel And Restaurant Business, Design, Clothing And Footwear, Construction, Transport And Communications, Printing And Publishing, Metalworking And Mechanical Engineering, Mining. The study involved 65% of women, 35% of men among teachers, 51% of women, and 49% of men among pupils.

The division prepared 32 questions, and after receiving answers from the above-mentioned vocational education institutions, two tables were prepared with a comparative evaluation of digital library services by teachers and pupils as a percentage.

Diagram 1

Diagram 1. Questions: 1. Do you perceive information better on printed media? 2. Do you perceive information better in soft copies? 3. Do you use information from the mass media? 4. Do you use information from educational institutions? 5. Do you use information from communicating with friends and acquaintances? 6. Do you use information from the Internet? 7. Do you use information from the library? 8. Do you use information from public organisations?

Diagram 2

Diagram 2. 9. Do you use information from other sources? 10. Evaluate the library's assistance in finding educational literature in the catalogue necessary for the educational process. 11. Evaluate the library's assistance in finding bibliographies concerning pre-set training or production topic. 12. Evaluate the library's assistance in working with its e-learning resources. 13. Evaluate the library's assistance for teachers and pupils in creating applications, messengers and social networks. 14. Evaluate the library's assistance in providing the electronic information needed for the learning process 15. Evaluate the library's help in the address links for finding the necessary electronic manuals and textbooks. 16. Evaluate the library's assistance with other issues that help improve the learning process.

Diagram 3

Diagram 3. 17. The attractiveness of the library during the period of distance (mixed) learning on the issue of learning to find the necessary sources of information for the educational process. 18. The attractiveness of the library in the period of distance (mixed) learning to expand the range of professional information services. 19. The attractiveness of the library in the period of distance (mixed) learning to create centres of social and psychological assistance. 20. Attractiveness of the library in the period of distance (mixed) learning in other areas. 21. How do you evaluate the library site regarding the availability of literature needed for the educational process? 22. How do you evaluate the library website as an assistant teacher during the educational process? 23. How do you assess the library's page on social networks as an aid in preparing and conducting classes? 24. How do you evaluate virtual exhibitions and book trailers on the library's website to support educational material for teachers and pupils?

Diagram 4

Questions: 25. How do you rate the video review of educational web resources posted on the library's website? 26. How do you assess the video review of textbooks and manuals, and other educational literature posted on the library's website? 27. How do you assess online meetings with interesting people on the library's website? 28. How do you evaluate the professional media courses that are posted on the library's website? 29. How do you assess the online master classes and pieces of training conducted by the library to help teachers and students? 30. How do you assess the online conferences, round tables, and conversations on professional topics held by the library? 31. How do you assess the demonstration of intellectual resources of teachers of your institution? 32. How do you evaluate additional library services: copying and scanning documents; working on the computer and the Internet; co-working etc.

CONCLUSIONS

Social networks are news exchange services where each user is both an author and a reader. In their activities on social networks, libraries must adhere to certain principles under the media specifics of these resources. The first thing to understand is that the

static content of the institution's page does not play an important role in social networks. The library's profile on the social network is just a reference to it as a source of news. Therefore, the main task of creating a representative office in the social network is a constant, rhythmic generation of messages for the user's news feed. It is worthy of understanding the purpose of such activities in different ways. Thus, most pages of educational and research institutions on social networks only support the institution's official website by placing a link to the new information added to the site. It is necessary to consider such a strategy sufficient. Still, it does not use all the opportunities of social media, focusing only on the task of conveying existing information on the Internet to the user of the social network. However, if the page contains only a link to the site, it does not look very attractive. In addition, the administrators of such pages often do not describe what the user will find at the appropriate link, and why it is necessary for them.

Vocational education institution libraries should pursue an active policy of promoting their activities, as they do not currently have mass support and popularity.

Administering a page on a social network requires a clear strategy that contains answers to the question: what is the library's purpose in the social network? What is the target audience of the page? Accordingly, it is necessary to supplement, comment on links to materials on the institution's website, disseminate information on other pages and create its own content.

The users should like the page of the library which touches them. They should also expect the appearance of new functional and engaging materials; otherwise, there will be no reason to sign for page updates.

To implement the strategy of administering the library page on the social network requires the work of not only one responsible employee. In fact, this requires the coordinated work of the entire institution. The entire staff of the institution must work to ensure that the page has as much of its own original material.

Accordingly, there should be well-established interaction between employees:

Awareness of each other's activities and responsibilities. It applies to the individual scientific work of employees (information on participation in seminars, conferences, publications, etc.), and work directly in the institution;

All activities within the institution should be accompanied by the question: how can this be presented to readers, visitors, and partners?;

The institution should have its own mini-press centre: the point where all information will be collected, and where the selection and processing of materials will occur (the absence of such a centre will lead to confusion, inconsistency, etc.).

Fulfilling all these requirements is possible both at the direct interpersonal level and with the assistance of a special organisation of internal seminars, meetings, etc. The priority is a strategy of a complete restructuring of the work organisation itself: employees' daily responsibilities should be determined by the requirement to cooperate with the institution's improvised "press centre". In other words, each employee's action must end with interaction with the administrator of the institution's page on social networks. Here it is necessary to make two remarks. First, indeed, in a way, the work of "collecting" information takes place in filling the institution's site. However, usually, only important and official information is posted on the site.

The frequency of updating such information in small institutions or departments is, at best, once every few months. It is clearly not enough for a page on a social network. In addition, this approach does not exhaust the possibilities of social media. Secondly,

it may seem that it is not worth so much effort to maintain a page on a social network. However, if there is a need to optimise the institution's work for the sake of such a page, it means that, in general, this work has not been focused on "exit". In modern society, this approach is unacceptable: there is only what there some information is in our time. In addition, not just any information, but one that is available to members of society, is included in the communicative space, which practically means – available to Internet users. The best way to integrate information into users' communication is to introduce it as social media material because, in this case, users themselves reproduce it as authors and distribute it further on a network basis.

Thus, the page in the social network should be filled with the institution's own content, using all the features and peculiarities of social media; otherwise, its existence will be purely formal. The administration of such a page is important not only because of the need to promote the activities of scientific institutions and specialised foundations. Active work on the institution's presentation helps to optimise the organisation of work of employees of the institution, highlighting the ultimate goal of any element of its activities, which is to "exit" the product to the outside, to a potential consumer. Suppose the work on the institution's representation in social media does not cause changes within the institution. In that case, it can mean one of two things: either the organisation of work has been already carried out at a high level, and the necessary information is constantly accumulated to work in social networks, or this work is purely formal, hence ineffective.

The lack of blogs in libraries forces us to look for options that will assist in formulating a goal for creating a blog:

Show that the library is a modern institution that is ready for constructive communication, criticism, change and innovation;

Improve communication with potential users through dialogue and comments;

Promote information or other services among readers who search for information on the Internet, including in the blog;

Increase the brand awareness of the library so that more people can answer the question "What is a library?" and "Why do you need it?";

Conduct surveys and receive instant answers from readers; keep in touch with readers: as a rule, while the blog is updating, they receive messages (another strong proof that you need to write regularly);

Disseminate information about book collection services and get people to talk about them;

Communicate with the media because many journalists use blogs and microblogs while preparing reports and stories; attract new employees.

It is also necessary to solve problematic issues in the formation of virtual exhibitions with links to the full-text version of the publication, to direct user interest to Internet resources where you can buy the necessary literature or provide links to book search systems on the Internet, links to libraries. Although these actions do not correspond to the main task of the book exhibition in its traditional sense, however, according to the philosophy of the integrated information space, the library does not lose a user but gains. Having received a similar information service on the library server, the user will return to it repeatedly.

In addition, while creating virtual exhibitions, the use of Internet resources, and links to electronic sources of information retrieval give a positive effect. However, this cannot replace the exhibition itself but will only serve as additional opportunities.

In addition, it should be noted that an important condition for a quality library site is the following:

Visiting the site, the user must get a complete picture of the library: general information (name, mission, structure, rules of use, contacts);

News concerning planned or held events and promotions, information (new acquisitions, periodicals) and electronic (E-catalog, virtual exhibitions) resources;

Library services and projects.

According to the survey, not all libraries follow the rules mentioned above.

The most negative moment in the work of vocational education institution libraries in Ukraine (based on the example of three regions) was the attractiveness of the library during the period of distance (mixed learning). Almost all respondents negatively assessed the work of the library during this period, in particular, taking into consideration the pandemic COVID-19. Therefore, there is a necessity for targeted work with library staff to conduct relevant seminars and conferences on this issue.

Considering those mentioned above, the Division of Scientific and Methodological Support of Vocational Education at the Institute of the Education Content Modernization State Scientific Institution decided to organise and hold a number of online seminars for librarians of VEI to improve their activity in the information and communicative space.

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ДІЯЛЬНІСТЬ БІБЛІОТЕК ЗАКЛАДІВ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ (ПРОФЕСІЙНО-ТЕХНІЧНОЇ) ОСВІТИ В ІНФОРМАЦІЙНО-КОМУНІКАТИВНОМУ ПРОСТОРИ

Метою статті є систематизувати, узагальнити нові знання щодо діяльності бібліотек закладів професійної (професійно-технічної) освіти в інформаційно-комунікативному просторі, розглянути конкретні види діяльності з погляду сьогодення та перспектив їх розвитку.

Методологія дослідження базувалася на загальнонаукових принципах єдності теорії і практики, системності, комплексності, усебічності пізнання. Досягненню поставленої мети сприяло використання загальнонаукових (опису, аналізу, синтезу, порівняння, узагальнення) та спеціальних (бібліографічного, вибіркового спостереження, групування, контент-аналізу) методів на емпіричному та теоретичному рівнях дослідження.

Наукова новизна дослідження полягає в узагальненні і систематизації нових та відомих знань щодо діяльності бібліотек закладів професійної (професійно-технічної) освіти в інформаційно-комунікативному просторі з погляду сьогодення та перспектив її розвитку в межах одного дослідження.

Основні висновки. Сучасні умови трансформації процесу навчання, орієнтованого на дистанційну освіту, та стрімкий розвиток цифрових технологій ставить перед бібліотеками закладів професійної (професійно-технічної) освіти (далі – ЗП(ПТ)О) нові виклики. Карантинні обмеження, з якими бібліотеки зіткнулись у 2020–2021 роках, продемонстрували необхідність швидкого переформатування різних видів бібліотечних послуг у онлайн-формат. Найперспективнішим каналом просування будь-якої інформації або ресурсів сьогодні є інтернет.

Використання інтернет-технологій у бібліотеках наразі є обов'язковим для кожного фахівця з бібліотечної справи. Бібліотекарі повинні не лише орієнтуватися в питаннях інформаційно-комунікаційних ресурсів та технологій, зокрема інтернету, але й застосовувати ці знання на практиці.

Таким чином, упровадження інтернет-інструментарію в діяльність бібліотек ЗП(ПТ)О є нагальною потребою. Існує велика різноманітність інтернет-сервісів, які можуть ефективно використовуватися бібліотекарями у щоденній роботі та дозволять вивести інформаційно-бібліотечне обслуговування бібліотек ЗП(ПТ)О на якісно новий рівень.

Ключові слова: бібліотеки, заклади професійної (професійно-технічної) освіти, інтернет, соціальні мережі, інформаційно-комунікативний простір.

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